

Isolation distance for producing hybrid rice seed

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The isolation distance for producing pure breeder and foundation seed of rice is 5 and 3 m, respectively. But these isolation distances do not apply to hybrid rice seed production that involves the use of CMS lines. We studied the present isolation distance for hybrid seed during 1988 and 1989 wet seasons. Pollinator V20 B was sown 1 wk after CMS V20 A, to synchronize flowering. V20 A was transplanted in rows against V20 B in the prevailing wind direction. In 1988, V20 A was transplanted in 25-m rows. Seed set along the whole row length (Table 1); it was highest (6.24%) at 1 m from V20 B and lowest (1.03%) at 25 m.

In 1989, V20 A was planted in 50-m rows. Highest seed set was 8.95% at 1 m; the lowest was 0.3% at 31 m (Table 2). Temperature during flowering ranged from 28 to 31 °C, relative humidity was 64-77%, and wind velocity 4.4-8.0 km/h.

The data indicate that rice can disperse its pollen up to 31 m: isolation distance should not be less than 31 m for producing pure hybrid rice seed. ■

Table 1. Seed set on male sterile line (V20 A) by distance from pollinator (V20 B). Ludhiana, India, 1988.

Distance from pollinator (m)	Seed set (%)			
	Row I	Row II	Row III	Mean
1	6.0	8.3	4.4	6.2
2	4.5	4.6	4.1	4.4
3	5.3	4.0	4.0	4.4
4	4.1	2.5	4.2	3.6
5	4.0	3.1	2.7	3.2
6	5.1	3.8	3.3	4.1
7	2.8	1.7	1.4	2.0
8	2.7	-	2.0	2.4
9	2.4	1.4	3.5	2.4
10	4.2	1.1	1.5	2.3
11	3.1	1.6	2.8	2.5
12	1.6	1.7	2.1	1.8
13	2.4	2.4	1.6	2.1
14	1.6	1.9	2.1	1.9
15	2.1	1.3	1.5	1.8
16	1.4	1.0	-	1.2
17	1.2	1.1	2.2	1.5
18	2.3	1.3	1.4	1.7
19	1.2	2.9	0.7	1.6
20	-	1.4	1.1	1.2
21	2.8	1.6	1.0	1.8
22	1.5	1.7	1.9	1.7
23	2.9	1.2	1.3	1.8
24	1.4	1.2	1.4	1.2
25	1.1	1.0	1.0	1.0

Table 2. Seed set on male sterile line (V20 A) at various distances from pollinator (V20 B). Ludhiana, India, 1989 wet season.

Distance (m)	Seed set ^a (%)					Mean
	Row I	Row II	Row III	Row IV	Row V	
1	5.7	12.3	9.4	8.0	9.4	9.0
2	2.6	1.4	7.5	8.2	4.8	5.3
3	-	3.4	5.2	10.1	1.5	5.0
4	2.8	1.9	2.3	8.4	2.1	3.5
5	-	4.8	2.6	5.2	1.9	3.6
6	1.3	-	0.9	2.6	3.6	2.1
7	1.7	4.8	1.6	0.9	5.3	2.9
8	3.2	5.6	1.9	1.3	4.9	3.4
9	3.6	2.3	2.5	1.1	3.5	2.6
10	1.9	0.8	2.4	3.9	1.4	2.1
11	3.8	2.6	1.5	1.7	-	2.4
12	1.8	1.2	4.6	4.1	2.1	2.8
13	2.8	1.6	4.0	2.5	3.8	2.9
14	2.2	1.4	1.6	2.1	1.6	1.8
15	2.2	5.1	1.1	1.4	1.1	2.2
16	-	1.8	2.2	0.7	0.8	1.4
17	1.9	3.5	1.9	1.3	2.6	2.3
18	2.5	-	1.9	2.0	1.9	2.2
19	0.8	2.0	1.7	0.8	-	1.3
20	3.0	1.1	2.0	1.5	-	2.0
21	3.9	2.1	0.8	1.2	1.7	1.9
22	0.6	4.5	0.9	0.8	1.2	1.3
23	1.1	0.9	1.5	1.6	0.7	1.2
24	1.3	0.9	0.5	1.1	1.4	1.0
25	1.2	1.2	2.1	1.1	-	1.7
26	0.5	1.4	2.2	1.0	0.5	1.2
27	1.7	1.8	1.5	1.4	0.5	1.4
28	1.9	1.1	1.3	-	-	1.3
29	0.8	0.8	0	0.9	1.0	0.7
30	0	1.3	0.9	0	0	0.4
31	0	0.6	0	1.0	0	0.3

^aNo seed set on rows 32-50 m from V20 B.

Identification of potential maintainers and effective restorers for CMS lines

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We evaluated spikelet sterility and pollen sterility of 25 CMS lines during kar (Jul-Oct) 1989 to identify stable CMS lines.

Five showed male sterile stability:

	Pollen sterility (%)	Spikelet sterility (%)
V20 A	98.0	98.4
ZS97A	98.0	98.7
IR46828 A	97.1	95.6
IR46830 A	97.3	96.7
IR58025 A	96.0	94.0

Spikelet sterility in the other lines did not correlate with pollen sterility. There was also plant-to-plant differences in pollen sterility in the same CMS line.

During late samba (Nov-Mar) 1989-90 we evaluated spikelet fertility in the F₁s of 24 crosses involving CMS lines V20 A, IR46828 A, IR46830 A, IR54752 A, IR58025 A, and MS577 A and varieties IR36, IR50, IR64, CO 37, CO 43, Rasi, Jaya, ASD16, ADT36, AS34011, and TM4309. Potential maintainers were identified as having >90% pollen sterility and <10% spikelet fertility and effective restorers as having <10% pollen sterility and >90% spikelet fertility.

Rasi, CO 37, ASD 16, and TM4309 were identified as potential maintainers; IR36 and IR50 as effective restorers for CMS line V20 A. IR50 was identified as an effective restorer for CMS line IR46828 A.

The potential maintainers identified for V20 A are being used in the back-cross program to develop new CMS lines. The restorers identified for V20 A and IR46828 A are being used to develop new hybrid combinations. ■